

STUDIES ON SEED FATS OF CUCURBITACEAE FAMILY. PART II.
THE COMPONENT FATTY ACIDS OF *TRICHOSANTHES*
CUCUMERINA, LINN.

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The component fatty acids of *Trichosanthes cucumerina* has been investigated, using spectrophotometric and low-temperature crystallisation methods.

The seed fats of many members of the *Cucurbitaceae* family have been found to be rich in conjugated unsaturation. Compositions of the seed fats of other members of Cucurbitaceae family (Chakrabarty *et al.*, *Naturwiss.*, 1955, 42, 344) have indicated the possibility of their use as good drying oils like Tung oil. With that end in view studies in the seed fat of *Trichosanthes cucumerina* (Bengali-Banchichinga, N.O. Cucurbitaceae), a climbing annual, grown all over India, was undertaken.

In the present investigation modern methods including spectrophotometric technique, advocated by Hilditch *et al.* (*Analyst*, 1945, 70, 68; 1951, 76, 899; "Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", 3rd ed., 1956, Chapman and Hall, London) in conjunction with the low-temperature fractionation of fatty acids from organic solvents have been employed.

Fruits are oval or oblong and pointed; cells are imperfect. The fruits are from one to four inches long, and from one to one and a half inches in diameter. Till ripe, they are striated with white and green, and while ripe, they become red. Seeds are involved in a red pulp and 3/8"-1/2" size and half ellipsoidal in shape.

EXPERIMENTAL

The seeds were obtained from crops grown in Gujarat. The oil was extracted from ripe and dried seeds with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). The characteristics of the oil and seeds are presented in Table I. The percentage of unsaponifiables was determined according to the method recommended by the American Oil Chemists' Society (Official and Tentative Methods of A.O.C.S. Method Ca- 6a- 40, 1946).

TABLE I

Characteristics of oil and seeds.

Seeds :	Average weight of single seed (g.)	...	0.0994
	%Yield of oil (on whole seed)	...	28.0
Oil :	Ref. index (at 40°)	...	1.4881
	%Free fatty acids (as %oleic)	...	17.0
	Sapon. equiv	...	300.8
	I.V. (Wij's, 30 mins.)	...	134.7
	Unsaponified and unsaponifiable matters (%)	...	1.20
	%Saturated acids (Bertram's oxidation)	...	11.87

The mixed fatty acids of the oil were separated into different fractions of varying mean unsaturation by crystallising first from a mixture of ethyl ether and light petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and then from acetone at -50° and -60° respectively. The details of crystallisation are shown in Chart I. Three fractions, designated A, B, C in the increasing order of iodine value, were obtained. Their proportions are shown in Table III*. The original mixed fatty acids and the fractions A, B, C were examined separately by spectrophotometric method, the details of which are presented in Table III.

Specific extinction coefficient values taken for calculation are according to Hilditch *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE II

	Unisomerised. (268 m μ)	Alkali-isomerised. 170°/15 min. (268 m μ).	180°/60 min. (234 m μ).
α -Elaeostearic	780	1690	197
Linolenic	...	555	575
Linoleic	...	...	906

The saturated acids were determined in duplicate by Bertram's oxidation method (*Z. deut. öl-u. fett. Ind.*, 1925, 48, 733) as modified by Palikan and Von Mikusch (*Oil & Soap*, 1938, 15, 149) and the % oleic acid was obtained by difference.

CHART I

Low-temperature crystallisation chart.

TABLE III

Spectrophotometric data.

	Iodine value.	E _{1%¹cm} at 268 m μ . Unisomerised.	E _{1%¹cm} at 268 m μ . Iso-merised at 170°/15 min.	E _{1%¹cm} at 234 m μ isom. at 180°/60 min.
Mixed fatty acid	143.8	635.0	575.0	240.0
Fraction A	89.2	569.9	...	127.5
Fraction B	142.1	737.5	...	192.3
Fraction C	157.5	495.7	...	421.3

* The iodine values in these cases do not represent true iodine values because of the presence of conjugated system.

Since the oil contains tri-conjugated acid as one of the components, the iodine value is not an indication of mean unsaturation. Calculation of %oleic acid is therefore not possible from the iodine value. For this reason the %saturated acid in each fraction was determined by Bertram's oxidation method. The results are recorded in Table V along with data for component acids of different fractions.

About 7 g. of fatty acids (of I.V. nil), obtained by Bertram's oxidation method, was freed from unsaponifiable matter and converted into their methyl esters. The methyl esters were fractionated in an E.H.P. column and the saponification equivalent of each fraction was determined (Table IV). The proportions of different saturated fatty acids in the total saturated acids were calculated from these data, following the method of Hilditch (*loc. cit.*), and then distributed amongst the different fractions A, B and C in the same proportion as they were present in the total. The results are shown in Table VI.

TABLE IV

Fraction No.	Wt.	S.E.	C ₁₆ .	C ₁₈ .	C ₂₀ .
1	1.7910 g.	275.2 g.	1.4310 g.	0.3600 g.	...
2	0.6621	285.2	0.2565	0.3756	...
3	1.0020	287.8	0.3422	0.6598	...
4	1.4220	302.6	...	1.1700	0.2520 g.
5	0.7678	325.8	...	0.0050	0.7628
Residue	1.3130	326.0	...	...	1.3130
Total ex. non sap.	6.9579	...	2.0597	2.5704	2.3278
Wt. % of ester	...	...	29.61	36.94	33.46
Wt. % of acid in sat. acid	...	...	29.53	37.04	33.43
			Palmitic. (C ₁₆)	Stearic. (C ₁₈)	Arachidic. (C ₂₀)
% Acid in the whole m. f. a. (11.87 by Bertram's method)			3.51	4.4	3.96

TABLE V

Component fatty acids of different fractions.

Acids.	Fraction A. (19.58%).	Fraction B. (49.91%).	Fraction C. (30.11%).
Total saturated acids (by Bertram's method)	43.57	6.37	0.57
Palmitic	12.98	1.88	0.17
Stearic	16.29	2.36	0.21
Arachidic	14.70	2.13	0.19
Oleic (by difference)	16.91	39.69	31.14
Linoleic	7.10	12.50	40.44
Conjugated triene as α -elaeostearic	32.02	41.44	27.85

Palmitic, stearic and arachidic acids are distributed amongst the fractions A, B & C in the same proportion as in the total saturated acid.

TABLE VI

Components of different fractions (% ex N-S, in terms of total).

Acids.	A.	B.	C.	Total (% wt.)	Equiv.	Mole %.
Palmitic	2.59	0.94	3.05	3.58	0.01398	3.96
Stearic	3.25	1.18	0.06	4.49	0.01581	4.48
Arachidic	2.94	1.06	0.05	4.05	0.01295	3.68
Oleic (by diff.)	3.38	19.83	9.38	32.59	0.11200	31.71
Linoleic	1.42	6.24	12.17	19.83	0.07081	20.04
Conjugated triene as α -elaeostearic	6.40	20.67	8.39	35.46	0.12760	36.13

DISCUSSION

The seed fats of the N. O. Cucurbitaceae show two trends. In a large number of them the component acids belong to simple type, e.g. palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic, with saturated acids approaching 30% of total acids. In a few genera, however, presence of conjugated triene acids has been detected. Recently, this has been established with much greater accuracy. For example, *Momordica charantia*, *Trichosanthes anguina*, *Telfaria occidentalis* and others have been found to contain from 20 to 50% of conjugated triene acid. The present analysis of *T. cucumerina* seed fat has been compared with some of these in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Acids.	<i>M. charantia</i>					
	<i>Muricata</i> ¹ .	Proper ² .	<i>T. anguina</i> ³ .	<i>T. cucumeroid</i> ⁴ .	<i>T. occidentalis</i> ⁵ .	<i>T. cucumerina</i> .
Saturated	30.47	25.90	20.70	9.0	19.0	11.87
Oleic	12.21	15.28	32.10	20.0	23.0	32.59
Linoleic	8.83	18.48	21.30	42.0	23.0	19.83
Conjugated triene acid (as α -elaeostearic)	48.49	40.34	25.90	29.0	19.0	35.46

1-3. Chakrabarty, *loc. cit.*4. Toyama & Tuchiya, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1935, 38, 185B.5. Hilditch & Riley, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1946, 68, 74.

It will be clear from the comparison that the seed fat of *T. cucumerina* is different from that of *T. cucumeroid*, reported by Japanese workers (*loc. cit.*), by its containing higher percentage of conjugated triene and lower percentage of linoleic acid and higher percentage of oleic, while the content of saturated acids is practically the same. The difference in composition between *T. cucumerina* fatty acids and that of another genus of *Trichosanthes*, namely *T. anguina*, reported by Chakrabarty *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), is less pronounced, and can be assumed to be the normal variation amongst the same genus. The difference in composition from the genus *Momordica* will be at once obvious from the higher percentage of saturated acids and conjugated triene acids and lower % of oleic and linoleic acids in the latter.

Another remarkable feature of the *T. cucumerina* seed fat is the presence of quite a high percentage of arachidic acid, which has hitherto not been reported in this type of fat. The presence of about 56% polyethenoid acids in the total fat, of which more than half consists of conjugated triene acid, ought to make this fat utilisable either as such or after solvent seggregation, in the surface coating industry. It is to be noted that although the conjugated triene acid has been estimated and recorded as α -elaostearic acid, it is most likely that they are present in the form of its geometrical isomer, trichosanic acid, as shown by Ahlers *et al.* (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 603 ; *Nature*, 1954, 173, 1045) in the case of conjugated triene acids, obtained from other members of 'Cucurbitaceae' family.

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